

MOBILE APPLICATIONS AS A LEARNING AI TOOL: A STUDY ON IMPROVING UNDERGRADS' ORAL COMPETENCE FOR JOB INTERVIEWS

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Abstract

In the modern era, effective communication skills have become increasingly important for individuals belonging to Generation Z and Generation Alpha. This is due to their immersion in a highly digital and interconnected world, where interpersonal interactions are often facilitated through online platforms and technology. These generations, particularly Generation Z, have been shaped by the digital age from the very beginning of their lives. Research on Generation Z has revealed that their strong familiarity with technology, especially communication tools, has profoundly influenced their communication preferences and habits. They have grown up in a time when the internet and mobile technology are integral parts of their daily lives, and even their most essential needs are often associated with internet access. Both the professional and personal existence are significantly influenced by it. Effective communication ensures seamless functions, top-notch performance in the AI learning environment, elevated job prospects and organizational expansion. The study aims to investigate how useful mobile application such as JobWhiz: AI Interview Prep as a teaching aid is helpful to under grades to become more proficient speakers of English to prepare and ace the Job Interview. The study employed descriptive analysis with a quantitative approach to validate the purpose of the paper. The sampling unit includes 50 students from the undergraduate level from various private colleges in nearby districts of Hyderabad in Telangana. A structured questionnaire (five Likert scales) was administered to collect the quantitative data. Additionally a pre-test and post-test on speaking abilities was conducted over the course of a month. Based on the outcomes, the findings underwent analysis, evaluation, and interpretation. The results of the research demonstrate a noteworthy improvement among the learners' oral proficiency after using the free mobile application.

Keywords: Gen-z & Gen Alpha, Mobile Application, Communication Skills, Oral Proficiency, Job-Interview, AI.

1. INTRODUCTION

ICT

Speaking builds good societal relationships and connects the global world. It can influence the audience if the speaker tries to persuade and motivate with effective thoughts, varied ideas, and a highly influential style of speech delivery. In every educational sphere, language instructors and learners face several challenges in transferring true knowledge among themselves in a prompt manner. As defined by Harmer (2007), speaking is the willingness to communicate concisely and successfully; it doesn't depend on a thorough understanding of linguistic features. It aims to cautiously comprehend the use of words and specific information in meaningful communication.

Communication through speech was ranked amongst the most significant three talents as identified by Maes, Weldy, and Icenogle (1997) as being necessary for managing success. However, several studies conducted over several decades have shown that recent graduates lack adequate oral communication abilities, Bolt-Lee &

Foster, (20030; Reinsch & Shelby, (1997). Thus, it may be shown said that, there is a need for improvement in terms of effectively training students' communication abilities for the managerial job.

Employers and students have diverse perspectives on abilities like negotiating, oral communication, planning, problem-solving, and critical thinking. This demonstrates that there were issues with the educational system, which the institution needs to take seriously. (Pool & Sewell, 2007). Ng (2009) also looks into the opinions of employers on the employability of university graduates. Studying thinking, information, communication, technology, lifelong learning, worldwide view, and professional and cultural awareness were the nine employability skill qualities. The results indicated that graduates have modest employability abilities. (Rodgers, 2012).

Leveraging mobile technology for language acquisition has grown to be a predominantly effective mechanism in all spheres of educational organizations and workspaces. Sonmez et al. (2018) commented on the emergence of mobile educational systems and provided global access to learners in one go. To achieve better career prospects, one has to yearn for effective oral competence. They are desirous not only to get good credibility in academics but also to groom their personalities to succeed in the employment sector. Speaking skills are the building blocks of any language. The language learner should make sincere attempts to become proficient in pronunciation, apt vocabulary, and good intonation. English is intended to provide students with the essential skills required to communicate appropriately and effectively. (Davies,2000)

JobWhiz: AI Interview Prep:

This job interview practice app elevates the aspirations of job seekers with personalized suggestions, immediate feedback for deeper self- analysis with AI – Powered Job Interview App. The Job interview English Practice app has unique functions like The Job interview Stimulator which assists the user by stimulating a job interview environment. It poses some standard interview questions in English language and expects a genuine response from the respondents and also helps by sample responses for further references. This assistance creates a real-time experience and motivates the user to built the confidence and talk fearlessly. Furthermore, the app includes customized recommendations for the prospective employees who find it hard to answer during the interview. The personalized answers offer Sample scope to strengthen and give valuable industry insights to face the challenges. Expert Guidance is another crucial attribute, which facilitates the coaching tips and instant feedback on every query from very own personalized AI Job Coach. To add on, the app has performance tracking function that allows the user to check the progress, figure out areas for growth and watch your confidence surges. The AI tool furthermore comprises the Mock Interviews, which creates an real time environment for any job and enables you to improve and practice interviewing techniques to refine your skills and tackle any queries thrown your way. Consistent attempt to impress with effective talk, will defiantly make anyone stand out from the crowd. The recruiters might get convinced with the polished, refrained noteworthy responses which reflect the job seekers' unique abilities. This mode of practices helped thousands of job seekers who could ace their interviews and landed dream jobs and embarked new journey towards career success. These tutorials aimed to assist the user with different ideas by exemplification. The answers designed support

the respondent to understand the proper sentence pattern to speak in the target language more precisely. This mobile app has high-quality audio recorder to rehearse the voice modulation. In a nut-shell the mobile assisted language tool not only tailors your spoken Oratory skill for attending a job interview or business but also expands a broad avenue to showcase your true potential in accomplishing your dreams

Figure 1: Source: Google Play

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Recent studies and developments in mobile applications have shown their potential as beneficial assets for mastering a language. Web 2.0 interactive resources along with the applications of mobiles has gained traction in diverse educational settings (Kusuma et al., 2022). These technological resources offer a wide array of didactic possibilities for improving students' language skills, particularly in the context of improving German-language lexical competence. The below mentioned sources allude to the fact that mobile applications can be tailored to support language learning, from pronunciation enhancement to vocabulary acquisition and oral competence. Additionally, recent studies have indicated that mobile applications provide better results than traditional methods in language learning, math, and writing.

Krishnappa Preetham (2020) recommends different mobile applications such as Hello English, Busuu, Beelingu, GRE Prep & Practice, Awabe, BBC Learning English, Anki, The British Council, Lingbe, Italki, Anki, Ling Q, TOEFL iBT Preparation, IELTS Word Power, Duolingo, and Quiz Your English is exposed to the 100 undergraduate students in Bengaluru. The objective of this mobile-assisted learning language was to strengthen the English speaking skills. The experimental study supported those undergrads in learning to acquire the language and practice it well in their conversations by utilizing technological development.

Xiaoyu Fan et al. (2023) discuss in their experimental study mobile apps for English language learning. They have provided thoughtful insights about the user-friendly designs, the variety of learning material and its effectiveness in improving English skills. The paper tried to analyze the literature review of the past ten years concerning the favorable and negative aspects of learning with mobile gadgets. It discusses the theories surrounding the mobile-assisted language learning, tries to identify the positive and negative characteristics of the mentioned MALL and advocates for

the students' interior and exterior learning environment. The assessment indicates that all English educators and developers should create an effective designs in mobile applications that can assist learners and instructors in fostering the best utilization of innovative teaching and learning platforms.

Anggraini Anggraini, Unpris Yastanti, Faisal Faisal, Mar 2023 in their research study have advocated in a detailed manner about the unique strategy employed in the classroom, termed as Classroom Action Research (CAR) design, which includes four different phases. This design was implemented on students in the Easy English Course, who had difficulty in English speaking. The research study conducted the phases of strategic planning, execution, keen observation and interpretation of the findings were reflected. It has incorporated different research instruments such as sheets, tests, questionnaires and drafted documentation. The experimental study has contributed various aspects for the development English language learning by using Hello English as mobile application. It highlights the significance of a technologically built language learning platform for enhancing oral skills and gives future implications to explore in this area.

Kim, Heyoung & Kwon, Yeonhee. (2012) in his research journal addresses two important aspects: firstly, the most common and the most distinctive elements of a Smartphone application and secondly, the benefits and drawbacks of employing such Smartphone apps for efficiently mastering languages. The study, initially tries to apply the evaluation criteria, especially the designed mobile based ESL software, later on , the functions of the selected mobile application was analyzed measuring three categories, L2 approaches, Content and Design and Technology. Eventually, the findings proves that there was a significant effect of ESL apps, as it offers a personalized access, flexibility to rehearsal and most importantly learner- centric. Nonetheless, the study limits itself, by providing room for the further studies to ponder on context-based and collaborative kind of learning and also suggests for thorough research study in order to provide better guidance for effective MALL practices.

Karmila Machmud, Ridwan Abdulah (2018) affirms in their study that students can overcome their anxiety levels in speaking English by using mobile phone. The study has employed quasi experimental researchable method to analyze the data collected through questionnaire from the classroom students who often face anxiety issues in speaking foreign language. The outcome of the research study assures that scores of learners who received instructions via mobile applications performed better academically when, compared to the conventional teaching approach in regards student's speaking competence. Therefore, it can be concluded from the learning achievements of the experimental study that, the incorporation of mobile programs has minimized the students' anxiety levels from higher degree to lower degree level. However, the study limited itself by generalizing the sample size and the characteristics of the participants and also conducted the learning achievements on self-report measures, which may lead to biases.

Rizky Vita Losi, (2022) puts forth an unique mobile collaboration tool termed as Altissia as learning device to the students who are facing problem in acquiring the English speaking skills. The study investigates on the perceptions of students on MALL, specifically Altissia. Initially, none of the students were accessing aforementioned apps, which lead to low ability in their speaking competency. By the end of the experimental study, the questionnaire, provides the results that on an average,

majority of the students' perceptive has been changed and found a strong impact on their listening skills and also retaining capacity of vocabulary knowledge. Eventually, the students interest and their motivation towards learning process affirms that , the Altissia, mobile application media has improved students' speaking skills in their EFL class environment.

Aziz, Asma & Hassan, Mehmood & Dzakiria, Hisham&Mahmood, Qaisar. (2018), claims in their study, that mobile learning platform has gained its significance among the higher secondary school students in Pakistan. Data was collected randomly from survey done in the district of Okara (Punjab), Pakistan and a questionnaire was administered to collect the quantitative data to analyze on SPSS. The findings of the experiment based on the average score and frequency levels of the students demonstrates that they have shown great interest to use mobile learning devices in learning process. Because it makes their work easy and can enhance their communicative skills independently. Additionally, it provides self-evaluating strategies.

Ta'amneh, Mohammad. (2021) has conducted a research study on students enrolled in the first semester of various English speaking courses offered in the Badr Branch of Taibah University (Badr Branch). The chief goal of the project was to probe on the prospective of utilizing mobile assisted language learning technologies for honing proficiency in English. A questionnaire on the previous literature was administered among the sampling unit of 151 students, to find out to which level of agreement they have towards the given criteria. The study's investigator has used the Statistical software Package for Social Sciences by considering the average results and different standard deviations. They study ended with a positive feedback that defends the claim that smart phones provides friendly access and great ability to learn among the students group

Darsih, Endang & Asikin, Nida. (2020). Many research studies have been conducted on MALL, but this paper tried to investigate on the university students' perceptions towards the mobile learning in developing English speaking skills. The experimental survey was conducted on 96 students. A structured questionnaire and unstructured talks were employed used to compile the essential informaiton. It allowed the students to download free mobile applications such as Elsa Speak, Kamusku, Google Meet, YouTube, Zoom and Google Translate and use them for up skilling the language competency. The findings reveled that, the mobile applications provided an easy access and was very useful in assisting them to learn English fluently and flawlessly.

M, Sarpparaje, 2017, affirms M. Lorillard (2012) statement that, classroom instructors must transform into designers of effective educational learning environments. This serves the basis for the foundation of this research study TIRF, 2017). One of the most gratifying things one can obtain in a life time is getting mastery over the language, which retains eternal. This can be attained either by the conventional approach such as reading lessons and practice. Nonetheless, smart phones have rendered language learning easier in recent years. In the marketplace, the tiny forms of software is available that are known as mobile application. This app has secured a staggering pace within a few years of the official launch of the Google Play app store and the iTunes app store in 2008. It provides 2.6 million apps to the users. This incredible volume of the apps is designed for L2 or the foreign language learners. This apps offers wide range of assistance in teaching and learning from improving pronunciation, vocabulary to comprehensive language courses (DocPlayer,n.d.). The study suggests

these apps generate gamified learning educational opportunities contradictory to the traditional language learning methods. Being that, mobile phones are commonly accessible, language learning can be done even in the outdoors, by virtual learning in a real-life circumstances. This Study illuminates on the numerous ways to foster language development by collaborating with technology. The asserts that, the language learning programs offers a variety of techniques and materials for language acquisition which are very simple, approachable and more enjoyable.

Awadhiya, Ashish K & Miglani, Anshu. (2016) argued that mobile learning assistance has grown as a remarkable moment in the realm of Open and Distance Learning (ODL).It has eliminated all the impediments like time and location to learning environment, by placing the learning possibilities at the fingertips. The study tried to investigate the different barriers which Indian Open Universities' trainers might encounter while implementing m-learning.

Thirumangai Rajendran and Melor Md Yunus, (2021) in their research study had emphasized on the effectiveness of using potential instructional approach like Mobile Assisted learning to acquire the speaking mastership. Among the listening, reading and writing skills, speaking skills remains apparently the challenging task for the EFL and ESL aspirants. The study has reviewed the relevant, past researcher's insights from the year 2016 to 2020. The finding of the study recommends that the potential mobile learning tool propagates the novel concepts of the constructivism theory, and supports the learners with befitting self-regulatory environment, free from stress and criticism. It promotes easy English speaking learning, according to situation and the need of the learner to implement the grasped subject efficiently.

Aremu Bamidele, A., (2021) investigated on the impact of mobile learning devices among students' performance and motivation derived from it, in learning actively, voluntarily to achieve great heights .Fifty Nigerian students from Federal University Oye Ekiti indulged in the research experiment as responders. Students' Learning Outcomes (SLOT) and Students' Motivation Questionnaire (SMQ) were filled out, as a research instrument to validate the content and confirmed the results by using Cronbach Alpha and Test retest as reliability trust. The findings of the research revealed a substantial gender gap in having the capacity to obtain motivation and meet learning objectives. The research undertaken confirms that the students who have ever utilized an mobile learning tool displayed a different motivations than studnts who haven't. Furthermore, the researcher recommends the teachers and the learners to adopt the new designs and structures of m-learning devices at the higher levels of education to compete and sustain in the digitalized world.

Abdulrahaman Almarshadi, et. al., (2019) advocated that mobile usage in today's context is pre-dominant. This mobile device has become the learning tools for acquiring the knowledge at one's convenient pace and place. This study mainly focuses on learners who want to adopt English as Foreign language. It's proved and discussed deeply in this study that students speaking abilities are improved by using mobile application as an instrument to disseminate the knowledge profoundly without any hesitation. The survey data after thorough analysis and interpretation confirms that mobile learning tools are very effective in developing English speaking skills among EFL learners.

Berita Mambarasi Nehe, et. al., (2023) recommended in his research study done on the 25 different college students that students are much inclined to profusely use this

new learning techniques outside the classrooms to enhance their English speaking skills. Mobile language learning devices in mobiles will assist with novel experiences to access easily any teaching materials at their flexible time and place. Because the mobile language learning are self-regulatory, students do not hesitate to explore and strengthen language skills by using different apps and feel free to involve themselves in the sophisticated features. They are actually endorsed by the invention of m-language learning apps to up skill themselves based on their requirements and learning patterns where ever and when ever.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher has examined the different mobile assisted tools to stimulate the students professionally, confidentially and spontaneously prepare for an English Job Interview. The students were guided with various modules to condensate freely, flawlessly and naturally. There are several Job interview preparatory apps like Jobwhiz: AI Interview Prep, PepTalk: Practice Interview, Interview AI, Interview Question and Answer, My mock interview, Student Visa Interview Prep, Interview preparation App, IT Interview Preparation App, HR Interview Question, Placement Preparation, Learn English Interview, Job Interview English Practice, Interview questions and Answer, Interview skills, AI Questions Generator, Ai Job Interview Coach Pro and so on. All aforementioned apps will help in to practice of interview and turn your mock interviews into triumphs. The mobile apps empower the students and young adults to surpass in any job interview. Because of it's unique features, it boosts the user's confidence levels and makes an expert by continues practices .Additionally, it provided an personalized, stress-free learning platform by prompting you with required hints to speak fluently.

The study has employed Job Interview English Practice (Convo-Interview) m- apps as a tool to measure the significant impact on the oral proficiency of English among the undergrads. The small scale research was conducted on 50 outgoing students of private degree colleges in the surroundings of Hyderabad, Telangana. The study adopted convenient sampling technique to accumulate the information. Analysis was carried out based on the quantitative data.

Figure 2: Research Model

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

Speaking Activity: Mock Interview

The Mock Interview are the best sources for practicing and improving the oral skills. It generates the realistic atmosphere and stimulates the preparedness for the various job positions. In the experimental study the criteria incorporated for the controlled and experimental speaking activity groups at the both the before and after test (pre-test result and post test result) were: the proficiency in English speaking skills, Critical thinking regarding facts and ability to speak in the English language, presenting technique, attentive listening and comprehension , pitch-shifting, the pace , the power and also non-verbal cues like Gestures and Postures

Hypothesis:

H01: There is no significant impact of using free mobile applications on improving English Speaking skills.

H1: There is a significant impact of using mobile applications on improving English speaking skills.

H02: There is a significant difference of pre and post test results on undergraduates' speaking skills who used a mobile app.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

H1: There is a significant impact of using mobile applications on improving English speaking skills.

To test the significant impact of mobile applications, 50 students were randomly selected from an undergraduate college. Their communication skills were tested based on three parameters communication skills, speech delivery, body language, vocabulary, and pronunciation, in mock interviews (MI) for the first 15 days. Again, those students were exposed to playing the exercises in an English mobile app for the next 15 days. After 15 days, those students were called to the English lab, and again, their communication skills were tested on those aforementioned parameters. In the present experiment, the independent variable was mock interview, whereas the dependent variable was communication skills. The mean score was compared in both situations, and the difference was measured. Before being exposed to the app it was considered a control group, and after practicing for 15 days the score was considered an experimental group.

Table 4.1: Results of Experiment

Groups	Mean Score	Standard Deviation score
Control Group (Pre-Test)	2.28	0.496
Experimental Group (Post-Test)	5.32	1.046

Sample size (n=50)

Table 4.1 demonstrates that there is a difference that exists between the control group (mean=2.28; SD=0.496) and the experimental group (mean=5.32; SD=1.046666233). Control group in the pre-test mean scores with respect to their experimental group in the post-test is compared to draw the conclusion. Based on the mean score, the alternate hypotheses H1 is supported. Hence, it can depict that there is as a significant impact of using free mobile applications in improving undergraduate students' oratory skills.

H0 2: There is a significant difference of pretest and post test on speaking skills of undergraduate students intervening mobile app.

ANOVA:

An Analysis of Variance or ANOVA test is often applied on three or more unrelated samples or groups to determine the difference between the researches. The other name of it is Fisher analysis of variance and it is the extended version of the z-tests and t-tests. It is a statistical tool to evaluate the difference in the means scores of more than two groups. It has two categories: one-way ANOVA and a two-way ANOVA. If one independent variable is used it is one-way ANOVA and usage of two independent variable is incorporated then it is termed as two-way ANOVA.

$F = MST/MSE$ ('F' refers to ANOVA Coefficient, 'MST' to Mean sum of squares due to treatment & 'MSE' to Mean sum of squares due to error.)

Table: 4.2 ANOVA Test

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Rows	33.76	49	0.68898	1.055	0.026055	1.607289
Columns	576	1	576	882	5.45E-33	4.038392
Error	32	49	0.653061			
Total	641.76	99				

In the above table:2, it can be interpreted sum of squares between rows and columns is measured as 33.76 and 576. The sample size is 50 and hence the df value is n-1 which is showing as 49. F value is 1.055 and value of p value of rows is 0.02 which is less than 0.05 and p value of columns is 5.45E-33. P value is determined to accept or reject hypothesis. As the values of p values are less than 0.05 it is significantly understood that the values of pretest and post test are independent to each other and there is clear comparison among the same. The values shows that there is great improvement of speaking skills in post test when compared to pre test after the intervention of mobile apps. Hence it can be understood that the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant impact of mobile applications on speaking skills is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4.3: Synthesis of Hypothesis

H1	There is a significant impact of using mobile applications in enhancing English speaking skills	A mean difference exists between the control group and experimental group	supported
H2	JobWhiz: AI Interview Prep Mobile Apps with a wide variety of functions and audio recording activities help the learner practice and develop their mock interview skills.		supported

5. DISCUSSION

The experimental study tried to investigate how mobile assisted learning devices like Convo Interview mobile application has affected the oral competency of undergraduate students. The an overall sample size selected for the study was 50 through the convenience sampling technique and the population into account were undergraduate students of private degree courses of Telangana State. Both the general and professional course students prefer Oral competencies, therefore both the categories are employed for the sample. In this type of study, the independent

variable Mock Interview (MI) i.e JobWhiz: AI Interview Prep mobile application is measured with oral skills like communication skills, speech delivery and body posture, which served as dependent variable. Both the variables are have been assessed in multiple levels. Since, every value measured were less than 0.001, it signifies that null hypotheses can be proven to be disapproved paving the way to embrace and acceptance of alternative hypothesis.

The first hypothesis, there is a significant impact of mobile applications on speaking skills is proved using standard deviation. The mean variations show that there is a great difference in pre test and post test in the variances of standard deviation. Thus alternative hypothesis is accepted. The second hypothesis is to compare the differences of pretest and post test of speaking skills intervening mobile applications. The statistical tool used is ANOVA and it is proved that the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

6. CONCLUSION

The mock interview evaluates the basic awareness of the students better employability. The JobWhiz: AI Interview Prep mobile app with AI powered tool provides better scope to practice the communication skills like ability to reach to the target audience and think on the facts, active listening and comprehension skills. The students should possess mental fortitude to comprehend the questions posed by the job interviewers. It also facilitates the ability to improve speech delivery mechanism by balancing the pause, pitch, power with sufficient mechanism.

To sum up these two factors mentioned above, intern helps to maintain the right postures, good eye-contact while attending the mock interview. Additionally the technical skills also play a crucial rule in seeking better employability. Thus, self-oriented learning avenues, students can formulate fundamental understanding of their comprehensive thinking, behavioral patterns, oral competency and try to live to the expectations of the organization.

The skills possessed by the job aspirants should also be used in post- interview. These little endeavors in learning process with the collaboration of Mobile assistance assist them to strengthen their confidence level to adapt several skills required to reach the employer's goal. The generation of learning is looking towards AI for quality information and delivery. Hence it is proved that AI is more helpful tool to improve speaking skills among undergraduate students.

Further Implication:

Furthermore, the experimental study leaves an enough scope to expand to various domains where extra interpersonal variables, such as behavioral patterns, nonverbal cues employed, right postures and gestures could be included for post-graduate level. It can be extended to all technical and non-technical students across all the disciplines, which involves STEM education. The study implies for further research among the job aspirants or unemployed candidates in comparison with the employers' perspective. The study can be progressed on the macro level by employing the stratified sample technique to calculate the un-employability rate of students who are unaware of using ICT tools, AI generated platforms to land into their desired goal effortlessly.

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